

Formation of acetone thiosemicarbazone complex of ruthenium via usual chelation and unexpected fragmentation : Characterization and catalytic application[†]

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Abstract : Acetone thiosemicarbazone (abbreviated as Hactsc) reacts with [Ru(trpy)Cl₃] in refluxing ethanol in the presence of triethylamine to afford [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)] as a purple solid. The thiocyanate ion is generated *in situ* via a ruthenium mediated C-N bond cleavage of acetone thiosemicarbazone. Crystal structure of [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)] has been determined, which shows that actsc is coordinated to the metal center as a mono-anionic bidentate NS-donor, along with a terpyridine and a N-bound thiocyanate. The complex is diamagnetic, and shows characteristic ¹H NMR signals and electronic transitions in the visible region. Cyclic voltammetry on [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)] shows an irreversible oxidation at 1.13 V vs SCE and an irreversible reduction at -1.24 V vs SCE. DFT calculation has been carried out to explain the electronic spectral, as well as electrochemical, observations. The [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)] complex is found to efficiently catalyze transfer-hydrogenation reaction.

Keywords : Acetone thiosemicarbazone, C-N bond cleavage, ruthenium complex, crystal structure and catalytic transfer-hydrogenation reaction.

Introduction

There has been considerable current interest in the chemistry of thiosemicarbazone complexes of the transition metal ions¹, largely because of their bioinorganic relevance. However, we have been exploring the chemistry of transition metal complexes of selected thiosemicarbazone ligands, with particular reference to the variable binding mode displayed by these ligands in their complexes², and the present work has originated out of our continued exploration. For this study, we have chosen acetone thiosemicarbazone (abbreviated as Hactsc) as the ligand and ruthenium as the metal center. Our earlier studies have shown that acetone thiosemicarbazone can readily bind to a metal center, via release of the acidic proton, as a NS-donor forming a five-membered chelate ring (**I**)^{2c}. As the source of ruthenium [Ru(trpy)Cl₃] (trpy = 2,2':6',2''-terpyridine) has been selected, which is well known to afford mixed-ligand complexes via facile displacement of chlorides by chelating organic ligands³. The initial goal of the undertaken study was to synthesize a

mixed-ligand acetone thiosemicarbazone complex of ruthenium with trpy as ancillary ligand, and examine the binding mode of the thiosemicarbazone in it. Reaction of acetone thiosemicarbazone with [Ru(trpy)Cl₃] has indeed afforded a mixed-ligand complex, but its composition has been found to deviate significantly from the expected one. Herein we describe the formation and characterization of this complex, and exploration of its catalytic properties.

Experimental

Materials :

Ruthenium trichloride was purchased from Arora Matthey, Kolkata, India. [Ru(trpy)Cl₃] was synthesized

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

by following a reported procedure⁴. 2,2':6',2''-Terpyridine (trpy) was procured from Aldrich. Thiosemicarbazide was purchased from Merck, India. Acetone thiosemicarbazone (Hactsc) was prepared by condensing thiosemicarbazide with acetone in hot ethanol. All other chemicals and solvents were reagent grade commercial materials and were used as received. Tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate (TBHP), obtained from Aldrich, and AR grade acetonitrile, procured from Merck, India, were used for electrochemical work.

Synthesis of complex :

[Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)] : To a solution of acetone thiosemicarbazone (59 mg, 0.23 mmol) in ethanol (40 ml) was added triethylamine (23 mg, 0.23 mmol) followed by [Ru(trpy)Cl₃] (100 mg, 0.11 mmol). The resulting mixture was then heated at reflux for 5 h to yield a dark purple solution. The solvent was then evaporated to give a solid mass, which was subjected to purification by thin layer chromatography on a silica plate. Using 1 : 2 acetonitrile-benzene as the eluant, a purple band separated, which was extracted with acetonitrile. Evaporation of this acetonitrile extract gave purple crystals of [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)]. Yield : 34%. Anal. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₉N₇S₂Ru : C, 45.97; H, 3.64; N, 18.77. Found : C, 45.88; H, 3.66; N, 18.75%; ¹H NMR⁵ : 7.70 (H, d, *J* 6.2), 7.65 (H, d, *J* 6.4), 7.17 (H, d, *J* 6.5), 7.18 (H, d, *J* 6.8), 7.20–7.36 (7H)*, 4.80 (s, NH₂), 2.17 (s, CH₃), 2.01 (s, CH₃); IR : 2096, 1628, 1517, 1463, 1448, 1384, 1364, 1301, 1280, 1245, 1159, 1048, 770, 730, 672 and 591 cm⁻¹. Electronic spectral data : (λ, nm (ε, M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)) : 505 (510), 316 (2900), 273 (3900), 239 (7000).

Physical measurements :

Microanalyses (C, H, N) were performed using a Heraeus Carlo Erba 1108 elemental analyzer. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured using a Sherwood MK-1 balance. ¹H NMR spectra recorded in CDCl₃ solution on a Bruker Avance DPX 300 NMR spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard. IR spectra were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum Two spectrometer with samples prepared as KBr pellets. Electronic spectra were recorded on a JASCO V-630 spectrophotometer. Electrochemical measurements were made using a CH Instruments model 600A electrochemical analyzer. A platinum disc working electrode, a platinum wire auxiliary electrode and an aqueous saturated calomel reference electrode (SCE) were used in the cyclic voltammetry experiments. All electrochemi-

cal experiments were performed under a dinitrogen atmosphere. All electrochemical data were collected at 298 K and are uncorrected for junction potentials. Optimization of ground-state structure and energy calculations were carried out by density functional theory (DFT) method using the Gaussian 03 (B3LYP/SDD-6-31G) package⁶. GC-MS analysis was performed using a Perkin-Elmer CLARUS 680 instrument.

X-Ray crystallography :

Single crystals of the [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)] complex were grown by slow evaporation of solvent from a solution of the complex in acetonitrile. Selected crystal data and data collection parameters are given in Table 1. Data were collected on a Bruker SMART CCD diffractometer using graphite monochromated MoKα radiation (λ = 0.71073 Å). X-Ray data reduction and, structure solution and refinement were done using SHELXS-97 and SHELXL-97 programs⁷. The structure was solved by the direct methods.

Table 1. Crystallographic data for [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)]

Empirical formula	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₇ S ₂ Ru
Formula mass	522.63
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	P2 ₁
<i>a</i> (Å)	8.0768(12)
<i>b</i> (Å)	16.447(2)
<i>c</i> (Å)	8.8833(12)
β (deg)	114.507(7)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1073.7(3)
<i>Z</i>	2
<i>D</i> _{calcd} (g/cm ⁻³)	1.617
<i>F</i> (000)	528
Crystal size (mm)	0.09 × 0.13 × 0.26
<i>T</i> (K)	273
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.947
R1 ^a	0.0547
wR2 ^b	0.1430
GOF ^c	0.99

$$^a R_1 = \frac{\sum |F_o| - |F_c|}{\sum |F_o|}$$

$$^b wR_2 = \frac{[\sum (w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2)] / \sum (w(F_o^2)^2)]^{1/2}}$$

$$^c \text{GOF} = \frac{[\sum (w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2) / (M - N)]^{1/2}}{\text{where } M \text{ is the number of reflections and } N \text{ is the number of parameters refined.}}$$

General procedure for the catalytic transfer-hydrogenation reactions :

In a typical run, an oven-dried 10 ml round-bottomed

flask was charged with the aldehyde/ketone (1 mmol), a known mol percent of the catalyst, and KOH (0.1 mmol) dissolved in 2-propanol (5 ml). The flask was placed in a preheated oil bath at the required temperature. After the specified time, the flask was removed from the oil bath and water (20 ml) was added, neutralized with 1(M) HCl, and extracted with diethyl ether (4–10 ml). The combined organic layers were washed with water (3–10 ml), dried with anhydrous Na₂SO₄, and filtered. Diethyl ether was removed under vacuum and the residue obtained dissolved in hexane and analyzed by GC-MS.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization :

As delineated in the introduction, the present work was initiated with the aim of preparing a mixed-ligand acetone thiosemicarbazone complex of ruthenium containing trpy as ancillary ligand. Accordingly, a reaction of acetone thiosemicarbazone was carried out with [Ru(trpy)Cl₃] in a 1 : 1 molar ratio in refluxing ethanol in the presence of triethylamine, which afforded a purple complex in low yield (12%)⁸. Preliminary characterization (microanalysis, IR, and NMR) data on this complex indicated the presence of a thiosemicarbazone ligand and a terpyridine in the coordination sphere, but they did not match exactly with the expected [Ru(trpy)(actsc)Cl] formulation. For an unambiguous identification of this complex its crystal structure was determined by X-ray crystallography. The structure of this complex is shown in Fig. 1 and selected bond parameters are given in Table 2. The structure shows that acetone thiosemicarbazone is coordinated to ruthenium in the expected NS-mode (I), and a trpy is also bound to the metal center in the usual fashion. Interestingly, the sixth position is found to be occupied by a thiocyanate ion, which is linked to ruthenium through the nitrogen. The observed bond distances and angles are found to be quite usual. This complex is therefore formulated as [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)]. In this complex ruthenium is nested in a N₅S core, which is distorted octahedral in nature as reflected in the bond parameters around the metal center.

Absence of any solvent of crystallization in the crystal lattice of [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)] indicates existence of intermolecular non-covalent interactions. A closer examination of the packing pattern in the lattice reveals that

Fig. 1. Structure of [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)] (hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity).

Table 2. Selected bond distances and bond angles for [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)]

Bond distances (Å)			
Ru(1)-S(1)	2.382(6)	N(1)-N(2)	1.45(2)
Ru(1)-N(1)	2.130(14)	N(2)-C(1)	1.33(3)
Ru(1)-N(4)	2.074(15)	C(1)-S(1)	1.699(18)
Ru(1)-N(5)	1.899(17)	N(7)-C(20)	1.10(2)
Ru(1)-N(6)	2.080(16)	C(20)-S(2)	1.677(18)
Ru(1)-N(7)	2.016(14)		
Bond angles (deg)			
S(1)-Ru(1)-N(5)	175.9(5)	N(1)-Ru(1)-S(1)	80.2(4)
N(1)-Ru(1)-N(7)	169.9(6)	N(4)-Ru(1)-N(5)	80.1(7)
N(4)-Ru(1)-N(6)	156.9(6)	N(5)-Ru(1)-N(6)	76.8(7)
Ru(1)-N(7)-C(20)	177.1(15)		
N(7)-C(20)-S(2)	180(2)		

non-covalent interaction of three types, viz. (thiocyanate)C-S... π interaction, (phenyl)C-H...C(thiocyanate) and (phenyl)C-H...C(methyl), are active within the neighboring complex molecules (Fig. 2). These intermolecular non-covalent interactions, extended throughout the entire lattice, account for the stability of the crystal.

The presence of a coordinated thiocyanate in this complex, and the absence of any recognized source of it during the synthesis of the complex, clearly indicates that it

Fig. 2. Non-covalent (C-S... π and C-H...C) interactions in [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)].

must have been generated *in situ* via fragmentation of acetone thiosemicarbazone itself. Generation of thiocyanate ion from acetone thiosemicarbazone via a C-N bond cleavage has recently been reported by us^{2p}. Some speculated sequences behind formation of [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)], that seem probable, are illustrated in Scheme 1. In the initial step one acetone thiosemicarbazone is believed to bind to the metal center in the NS-fashion (**I**) via displacement of two chlorides, while a second thiosemicarbazone remains linked to the ruthenium-bound chloride through hydrogen-bonding to generate an intermediate **A**. The metal center is believed to undergo a one-electron reduction by triethylamine at this stage. In the next step elimination of HCl takes place to generate a second intermediate **B**, where the second thiosemicarbazone is coordinated to ruthenium as a monodentate N-donor ligand. In the final step a C-N bond cleavage takes place affording [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)], along with elimination of acetone hydrazone.

Scheme 1. Probable steps behind formation of [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)].

The fact that two moles of acetone thiosemicarbazone are required for formation of one mole of [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)], one for chelation to the metal center in NS-mode (I) and the other to provide a thiocyanate via metal-assisted fragmentation, accounts for the poor yield of the complex from a reaction carried out with equimolar ratio of [Ru(trpy)Cl₃] and Hactsc. This is further supported by the fact that synthetic reaction carried out with a 1 : 2 mole ratio of [Ru(trpy)Cl₃] and Hactsc affords the same complex in better yield.

Spectral studies :

Magnetic susceptibility measurement shows that [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)] is diamagnetic, which corresponds to the +2 oxidation state of ruthenium (low-spin d^6 , $S = 0$) in this complex. ¹H NMR spectrum of [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)] shows two sharp signals at 2.17 and 2.01 ppm for the methyl groups in the coordinated acetone thiosemicarbazone, and signal for the NH₂ group is observed at 4.80 ppm. Signals for the coordinated trpy ligand have been observed within 7.1–7.7 ppm. Infrared spectrum of [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)] shows many bands of different intensities in the 400–4000 cm⁻¹ region. No attempt has been made to assign each individual band to a specific vibration. However, a sharp band at 2096 cm⁻¹ indicates presence of the coordinated thiocyanate ion. Comparison with the infrared spectrum of [Ru(trpy)Cl₃] shows some common vibrations (at 1448, 1384, 1280, 1245, 1159, 1048 and 730 cm⁻¹) due to the coordinated trpy ligand, and some new vibrations (at 1628, 1517, 1463, 1364, 1301, 770, 672 and 591 cm⁻¹) attributable to the ruthenium bound actsc ligand. The observed ¹H NMR and infrared spectral data of [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)] are therefore consistent with its composition.

[Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)] is found to be readily soluble in methanol, ethanol, chloroform, acetonitrile, etc., producing purple solution. Electronic spectrum of the complex has been recorded in methanol solution. Spectral data are presented in the experimental section. The complex shows several absorptions in the visible and ultraviolet region. The absorptions in the ultraviolet region are attributable to transitions within the ligand orbitals. To have an insight into the nature of absorption in the visible region, DFT calculations have been performed on [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)]⁶. Compositions of the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and the lowest unoccu-

piated molecular orbital (LUMO) are given in Table 3 and contour plots of these molecular orbitals are shown in Fig. 3. The HOMO has maximum (~56%) contribution from the coordinated thiocyanate, much less contribution from the metal center (~16%) and coordinated thiosemicarbazone (~22%) and ~7% contribution from coordinated trpy ligand. The LUMO is found to be delocalized primarily (~70%) on the coordinated trpy ligand, with much less contributions coming from the other fragments. The lowest energy absorption displayed by the complex at 505 nm is therefore assignable to a transition from a filled orbital of thiocyanate to a vacant orbital of trpy ligand.

Table 3. Composition of selected molecular orbitals of [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)]

Contributing fragments	% Contribution of fragments to	
	HOMO	LUMO
Ru	15.64	18.50
trpy	7.02	69.71
NCS	55.78	3.85
actsc	21.56	7.94

LUMO

HOMO

Fig. 3. Contour plots of the HOMO and LUMO of [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)].

Electrochemical properties :

The redox properties of [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)] has been examined in acetonitrile solution (0.1 M TBHP) by cyclic voltammetry (scan rate, 50 mV s⁻¹). The voltammogram, displayed in Fig. 4, shows an irreversible oxidation at 1.13 V vs SCE and an irreversible reduction at -1.24 V vs SCE. Based on the nature of the HOMO in this complex (Table 3), the oxidative response is assigned to an oxidation of the coordinated thiocyanate ligand. Similarly, based on the nature of the LUMO (Table 3), the reductive response is attributed to reduction of the terpyridine ligand.

to explore such possibility in the present complex where a pseudohalide (viz. thiocyanate) is bonded to ruthenium. We began our exploration by examining the transfer-hydrogenation of benzophenone to benzhydrol using [Ru(actsc)(trpy)(NCS)] as the catalyst precursor. After extensive optimization we found that 1.0 mol% catalyst, 0.1 mmol KOH, 2-propanol as solvent, a reaction temperature of 85 °C, and a reaction time of 8 h furnished an excellent yield (95%) of the targeted product (Table 4, entry 1). After successful transfer-hydrogenation of benzophenone, we have tried another aryl ketone (viz. *p*-

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammogram of [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)] in acetonitrile solution (0.1 M TBHP) at a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹.

Catalytic transfer-hydrogenation :

Catalytic transfer-hydrogenation of aldehydes and ketones, with 2-propanol as the reducing agent, has received considerable current attention⁹, mainly because of the green nature of the methodology, and complexes of ruthenium(II) have been very popular as catalyst for such reactions¹⁰. Ruthenium-catalyzed transfer-hydrogenation reactions proceed through the intermediacy of a ruthenium-hydrido species, and hence complexes with a potential for *in situ* formation of a Ru-H bond are suitable for trial as hydrogenation catalyst. As complexes with a Ru-X (X = halide) bond are known to provide a Ru-H fragment upon reaction with primary or secondary alcohols¹¹, we wanted

fluoroacetophenone) and three aryl aldehydes (viz. benzaldehyde, *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde and pyridine-2-aldehyde), and all of them could be reduced to their corresponding alcohols with yields varying from 53–92% (entries 2–5). The fact, that [Ru(actsc)(trpy)(NCS)] is found to efficiently catalyze transfer-hydrogenation of ketones and aldehydes using 2-propanol as the hydrogen donor, testifies that the Ru-NCS fragment in the catalyst precursor could be converted *in situ* to a Ru-H fragment. The observed catalytic activity of this complex is comparable to those of some reported ruthenium(II) complexes¹². There are three notable aspects of the observed catalysis : good yield, relatively mild reaction condition, and short reaction time.

Table 4. Catalytic transfer-hydrogenation of aldehydes and ketones^a

Entry	Substrate	Yield ^b (%)
1		95
2		87
3		76
4		92
5		53

^aReaction conditions : aldehyde or ketone (1.0 mmol), KOH (0.1 mmol), 2-propanol (5 ml), catalyst : [Ru(trpy)(actsc)(SCN)], reaction temperature (85 °C), time (8 h).

^bDetermined by GC-MS.

Conclusion

The present study shows that two molecules of acetone thiosemicarbazone readily react with a [Ru(trpy)Cl₃] molecule, and in course of the reaction one thiosemicarbazone coordinates to the metal center forming a usual chelate, while the other it undergoes an interesting metal-assisted C-N bond cleavage to generate a thiocyanate ion that remains bound to ruthenium. This study also shows that the mixed-ligand thiosemicarbazone complex of ruthenium can efficiently catalyze transfer-hydrogenation reaction.

Supplementary data

Crystallographic data have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, CCDC 1456471.

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